

NANOCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE-LIGNIN CARBON NANOFIBRES

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1 Objectives

This paper focuses on demonstrating the feasibility of electrospinning and carbonization of nanocrystalline cellulose (NCC)-lignin composite nanofibres.

2 Background

Lignin is one of the most abundant natural polymers, second only to cellulose. Lignin accounts for 30% of non-fossil organic carbon and constitutes between a quarter to a third of the dry mass of wood. Currently, a byproduct of paper-making, most lignin is used as a fuel. However, it is felt that value can be added to this non-petroleum renewable material by converting it to various material forms. Several studies have been conducted on converting lignin into fibrous form to serve as an inexpensive renewable precursor for carbon fibre.[1-3] However, the strength of lignin-based carbon fibre prepared through conventional melt or solution-spinning techniques is much lower than that of the petroleum-based pitch and poly (acrylonitrile) (PAN) carbon fibre.[1, 3]

We postulate that a stronger lignin fiber can be produced by encapsulating nanocrystalline cellulose (NCC) into electrospun lignin fibres to form composite nanofibres.

It is well known that nanoreinforcement can enhance material properties. NCC, which is extracted from cellulose, the most abundant renewable and biodegradable natural polymer is a very promising nanoparticle. The theoretical strength of NCC is estimated to be 10 GPa, which is almost three times stronger than commercial high performance fibres such as Kevlar® and Spectra®.[4] In addition, the diameter of electrospun fibres can be on the nanoscale, thus allowing the fibres to possess a relatively defect-free structure at the molecular level and thereby enhancing the possibility of producing strong composite fibres.

In order to fully realize the extraordinary properties of NCCs, it is necessary to maintain good alignment and uniform distribution within and along the lignin-based matrix fibre. However, it is challenging to achieve this goal due to the hydrophilic nature of NCCs and the extreme fineness of NCC which impedes the dispersion and orientation of NCC in the hydrophobic lignin matrix. To address this NCC water- in-oil (W/O) lignin emulsions were prepared; an NCC aqueous suspension was added to a water immiscible lignin continuous phase. NCC W/O lignin emulsions were electrospun into NCC filled lignin composite nanofibres.

3 Approach

NCC-lignin emulsions were prepared by adding the NCC aqueous suspension to the 35 wt% lignin/PEO (99:1) DMF/toluene (7:3) solution. The surfactant, Span 80, was added to stabilize the emulsions. This two-phase system was vortexed at 3000 rpm for 2 minutes and subsequently sonicated in a bath sonicator for 1 hour (Branson Bransonic ® 3510 5.5L MT UltraSonic Bath Cleaner). The emulsion system was then electrospun into nanofibers. The as-spun fibers were thermostabilized in air with heating rate of 1°C/min and held at 250°C for 1 hour and carbonized in N₂ at 1000°C for 1 hour with heating rate 10 °C/min.

4 Results and discussions

Fig.1 shows an optical image of the NCC-lignin emulsion droplets. Fig.2 shows an SEM image of the carbonized emulsion-spun NCC-lignin fibers. It can be seen that continuous NCC-lignin fibers were successfully electrospun and carbonized into nanofibres.

Fig.1. Optical image of NCC-lignin emulsion droplets

Fig.2 SEM image of carbonized NCC-lignin fibers

5 Conclusions

In this work we have demonstrated the feasibility of electrospinning and carbonization NCC-lignin composite nanofibers. This was accomplished by emulsion electrospinning wherein the hydrophilic NCC was encapsulated by the hydrophobic lignin phase. Further optimization of the process and characterization of hybrid NCC-lignin composite carbon fibres is in progress.

References

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